

Obscenity in Films and the Law

Manisha Saini¹ & M.M. Feroze²

1. Associate Professor, Department of Law, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur (Uttar Pradesh)

2. Associate Professor, Department of Law, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur (Uttar Pradesh)

Received : 20/03/2021

1st BPR : 24/03/2021

2nd BPR : 01/04/2021

Accepted : 07/04/2021

Abstract

Sub clause (a) of Article 19 (1) of the Constitution of India guarantees to every citizen of India the freedom of speech and expression. But this freedom is not absolute and it is subject to reasonable restriction imposed by clause (2) of Article 19. Section 292 to 293 of the IPC prohibits the sale etc. of obscene books etc. and provide for their punishment. The purpose of this article is to discuss critically the various aspects of the law relating to obscenity along with the freedom of speech & expression.

Keywords: Obscene, freedom of speech & expression, morality and decency.

Introduction:

The literal meaning of the word "Obscenity" is lewd, impure, indecent, calculated to shock the moral sense of man by a discharged of chastity or modesty. According to Ramnath Iyear, the word "Obscenity cannot be said to be a technical term of the law and is not susceptible of exact definition in its judicial uses, though it has been defined in a general sense as meaning offensive to morality or chastity, indecent, nasty".

Laws against obscenity are made in the interest of public morality. Obscenity is connected with sex and sex in turn is related to love which is ultimately connected with the private life of people. Sex is one of the most important motivating forces of human actions and emotions. It is from these motives the feelings of love, jealousy and hatred etc. arise. Society must maintain a high degree of decency and morality, otherwise it would lead to licence and lewdness. At the same time the society should not for that purpose hamper the path of progress of mankind by restricting freedom of speech and thought.

Evolution And Background

In the famous case of **Queen V. Hicklin** (1868) 3QB 360, **Cockburn** C.J., laid down the test of obscenity in the following words: . . . *I think the test of obscenity is this, whether the tendency of the matter charged as obscene is to deprave and corrupt those whose minds are open to such immoral influences, and into whose hands a publication of this sort may fall* . . . It is quite certain that it would suggest to the minds of the young of either sex, or even to the persons of more advanced years, thoughts of a most impure and libidinous character.

But later on this test has undergone changes in the hands of English judges. The present trend in England is to find the "*effect of the publication on the mind of an average man*" and then to decide whether the publication can be said to be obscene or not.

In America the Hicklin test has been rejected and the court in **Smith V. California** (1959) 361 US147 laid down the test of obscenity in the following words:

"..... whether to the average person applying contemporary community standards, the dominant theme of the material taken as a whole appeals to prurient interest."

Freedom of Speech and Expression under the Constitution of India:

The Constitution of India guarantees to every citizen right to freedom of speech and expression under Ar. 19(1) (a). Freedom of speech and expression means the right to express one's own convictions and opinions freely by words of mouth, writing, printing, pictures or any other mode. It thus include the expression of one's ideas through any communicable medium or visible representation. But this freedom of speech and expression is not absolute to allow anyone to do or say whatever he likes. Under Article 19(2) of the Constitution, reasonable restrictions on freedom of speech and expression can be imposed by the State on the grounds of decency and morality. The words decency or morality under Article 19(2) of the Constitution are words of wide meaning.

The test of obscenity is whether the tendency of the matter charged as obscene is to deprave and corrupt those whose minds are open to such immoral influences and into whose hands a publication of this sort is likely to fall.

The International Convention for the Suppression of the Circulation of and Traffic in Obscene Publications was signed at Geneva in 1923. To give effect to the above convention, the Indian Penal Code incorporated section 292 and 293.

Obscenity under Ipc and Other Legislations

The Penal Code was silent on the definition of word obscenity in the beginning, but with a view to make the existing law more definite and more clear the provisions were amended by Act XXXVI of 1969. Apart from Sections 292, 293 and 294 of I.P.C., there are other legislations also in this genre.

1. The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956.
2. The Cinematograph Act, 1952.
3. The Young Persons (Harmful Publications) Act, 1956.
4. The Postal and Telegraph Act, 1893.
5. The Sea Customs Act 1878.
6. The Drama Act 1876
7. The Indecent-Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act 1986.

Postal and Telegraph Act bans sending obscene things by post and telegraph. Sea Customs Act is also of the same type. Drama Act bans obscene dramas and Cinematograph Act provides for censorship of films. Young Persons (Harmful Publications) Act provides the restraint on publications of such figure and stories which may arise the anti social feelings, crime, violence and lustful tendencies in children and young persons. Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986 prohibits indecent representation of women through advertisement or in publications, writings, paintings, figures or in any other manner and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.

Section 292, IPC, does not define obscenity, it merely punishes obscene acts which every type it may be either selling, purchasing, keeping or producing. But after the XXXVI Amendment Act of 1969, clause (1) of Section 292 explains the expression obscenity in the same terms as in the Hicklin's rule. Section 292 merely enhances the punishment where the obscene acts are sold etc. to persons under the age of 20 years. Section 294 deals with an obscene act done in a public place.

Control on Freedom of Speech & Expression on Grounds Of Obscenity:

Section 292 of IPC imposes a restriction on the Fundamental Right of the individuals which is permissible under Art. 19 (1) (a) of the Constitution. This section has been protected keeping in view the interest of public decency and morality. Clause (2) of 19 provides that, "Nothing in sub-clause (a) of Clause (1) shall effect the operation of any law, or prevent the State from making any law, in so far as such law imposes reasonable restrictions on the exercise of the right conferred by the said sub-clause in the interests of the sovereignty and integrity of India, the security of the State, friendly relations with foreign State, public order, "decency or morality", or in relation to contempt of the court, defamation or incitement to an offence.

The words "decency or morality" are words of wide meaning. The word 'obscurity of English law is identical with the word indecency under the Indian Constitution. The test of obscenity is whether the tendency of matter charged as obscene is to deprave and corrupt those who minds are open to such immoral influence, and into whose hands – publication of this sort is likely to fall. Thus a publication is obscene if it tends to produce lascivious thoughts and arouses lustful desire in the minds of substantial number of that public into whose hands the book is likely to fall.

Section 292 is not invalid in view of Art. 19(2) of the Constitution. It embodies a reasonable restriction in the interest of the general public because the law against obscenity seeks no more than to promote public decency and morality. The validity of the section was challenged in the Supreme Court in **Ranjit D. Udeshi V. State of Maharashtra**, (AIR 1965 SC 881) Hidaytullah, J (as he then was) observed:

"No doubt this article (Art. 19) guarantees complete freedom of speech and expression but it also makes an exception in favour of existing laws which impose restrictions on the exercise of the right in the interest of public decency or morality speaking in terms of the Constitution it can hardly be claimed that obscenity which is offensive to modesty or decency is within the Constitutional protection given to free speech or

expression, because the article dealing with the right itself excludes it. That cherished right on which our democracy rests is meant for the expression of free opinions to change political or social conditions or for the advancement of human knowledge. This freedom is subject to reasonable restrictions which may be thought necessary in the interest of the general public and one such is the interest of public decency and morality. Section 292 I.P.C. manifestly embodies such a restriction because the law against obscenity, of course, correction understood and applied, seeks no more than to promote public decency and morality. The word obscenity is really not vague because it is a word which is well understood even if persons differ in their attitude to what is obscene and what is not".

The Supreme Court drew a distinction between vulgarity and obscenity also. The court observed:

"A vulgar writing is not necessarily obscene, vulgarity arises a feeling of disgust and repulsion and also boredom but does not have the effect of depraving, debasing and corrupting the morals of any reader of the novel whereas obscenity has the tendency to deprave and corrupt those whose minds are open to such immoral influences."

The Supreme Court in **Aveek Sarkar V. State of West Bengal** AIR 2014 SC 1495 held that the test laid down in *Hicklin's* case is not correct and rather applied "community standard test" to determine obscenity. According to this test a picture of a nude/semi nude woman as such cannot per se be called obscene unless it has the tendency to arouse feeling or revealing an overt sexual desire. The picture should be suggestive of deprave mind and designed to excite sexual passion in persons who are likely to see it. Only those sex related materials which have tendency of exciting lustful thoughts can be held to be obscene but the obscenity has to be judged from the point of view of an average person.

On the basis of "community standard test", Supreme Court in **Devidas Ramchandra Tuljapurkar v. State of Maharashtra** AIR 2015 SC 2615 held that breast of a woman fully covered with the arm of a man, a photograph of course semi-nude had no tendency to deprave and corrupt the mind of the people in whose hand the magazine or newspaper would fall.

In **N. Radhakrishnan v. Union of India** AIR 2018 SC 4154, the Supreme Court dismissed a writ petition seeking to ban a novel "Meesha" published in weekly 'Matrabhumi' on the ground that it was derogatory to temple going women and hurt the sentiments of a particular community. The Court held :

"Literature can act as a medium to connect the readers only when creativity is not choked or smothered. The free flow of the stream of creativity knows no bounds and imagination brooks no limits. A writer or an artist or any person in the creative sphere has to think in an unfettered way from the shackles that may hinder his musings and ruminations. The writer possesses the freedom to express their views and imagination and readers too enjoy the freedom to perceive and imagine from their own viewpoint. Sans imagination, the thinking process is conditioned. The creative voices cannot be stifled or silenced and intellectual freedom cannot be annihilated. It is perilous to obstruct free speech, expression, creativity and imagination, for it leads to state of intellectual repression of literary freedom thereby blocking free thought and the fertile faculties of the human mind and eventually paving the path of literary pusillanimity. If the wings of free flow of ideas and imagination are clipped, no work of art can be created. The culture of banning books directly impacts the free flow of ideas and is an affront to the freedom of speech, thought and expression. Any direct or veiled censorship or ban of book, unless defamatory or derogatory to any community for abject obscenity, would create unrest and disquiet among the intelligentsia by going beyond the bounds of intellectual tolerance and further creating danger to intellectual cowardice which is said to be greatest enemy of a writer, for it destroys the free spirit of the writer. It is only by defending the sacrosanct principles of free speech and expression and by safeguarding the unfettered creative spirit and imaginations of authors, writers, artists and persons in the creative field that we can preserve the basic tenets of our constitutional ideals and mature as a democratic society where the freedoms to read and write are valued and cherished."

P.S. Chaudhary analyzed the test of obscenity laid down by the Supreme Court in the *Udeshi's* case and observed:

"If we analyze the test laid down in *Udeshi Case*, we find that the court has defined obscenity as "treating with sex in a manner appealing to the carnal side of human nature or having that tendency."

Similarly the Court has tried to indicate when it will have the constitutional protection, by putting forward the theory of "Preponderating social purpose or profit". Therefore in our case the approach in any given case would be to find out:-

First *whether there is obscenity;*

Second *if there is obscenity, whether side by side there is social purpose or profit; and*

Third *if there is such a social purpose or profit, is it of a preponderating nature.*

It may be said that the test correctly tries to balance the interest of the individual's freedom of speech and expression against the interest of the society in preserving good morals.

The most alarming thing today is the increasing vulgarity in films. The situation had come to such a pass that one could not see films in the theatre or on television along with children. More and more double meaning songs are being used in films. The unhealthy trend had affected the country's cultural ethos. The Supreme Court realized the danger of such thing way back in 1965.

"Emulation by our writers of an obscene book under the aegis of this court's determination is likely to pervert the entire literature because obscenity pays and true art finds little popular support. Only obscurant will deny the need for such a caution."

Conclusion:

Everybody is feeling that things are really getting out of hand and the censor board is not properly doing its job. This concern is not misplaced since none of us would like a whole generation of young men and women to be constantly exposed to such grossness. The government has to take a serious note of this growing menace. Half hearted efforts will not bring any result. There is no reason why the legislature should not take the lead in undertaking legislation against others which are condemned by the consensus of opinion in this country and which may stand just beyond the reach of the existing law. The Ombudsman system may also be considered as an effective platform to channelize public resentment against the wide spread vulgarity of today.

References

1. Iyer's Law Lexicon, 1940, P. 894.
2. Harry M. Color: Obscenity and Public morality, P. 3 University of a Chicago Press, Chicago and London
3. M.B. Achwal: The literary aspect of obscenity p. 27, edited by A.B. Shaw in the Roots of obscenity.
4. V.G. Ramachandran: Fundamental Rights and Constitutional Remedies, P. 662 Vol. (1), 2nd Ed.
5. Amia, K. Sarkar: Literature and Obscenity (1962) 64 Bom. L.R. (Journal) 161.
6. (1868) 3 QB 360.
7. (1959) 361 US 147.
8. Section 292 (1) - "A book pamphlet etc. shall be deemed to be obscene, if it is lascivious or appeals to the purient interest or of its effect. .." Such as to tend to deprave and corrupt persons who are likely to read etc.
9. AIR 1965 SC 881.
10. (1965) I.S.C.R. 69, 70.
11. AIR 1986 SC 967.
12. Chaudhary P.S. : The test of Obscenity in Ranjit Udeshi Case, AIR 1969 (Vol. 56) P. 105.
13. Ranjit D. Udeshi V. State of Maharashtra AIR 1965 SC 881 (at page 880).
14. AIR 2014 SC 1495
15. AIR 2015 SC 2615
16. Wills — Constitutional Law and United States, 477.

